

THE ROLE OF ARTISTIC LITERATURE AND MUSIC IN FORMING STUDENTS' SENSE OF PATRIOTISM

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Abstract: In today's socio-cultural life, educating the young generation in the spirit of patriotism is one of the most urgent problems. The state policy in the field of education is aimed not only at fulfilling the social order of the state in the national education system, but also at educating a patriotic person with high moral qualities, who respects the individual rights and freedoms, traditions and culture of other peoples.

Key words: Patriotism, fiction, history, National art.

It is known from history that art and culture are one of the important factors of human development. The level of development of each society is determined by the development of art and culture in that society. Every ruler or statesman who lived in history had peace, prosperity and prosperity in his country only if he valued science, culture and art in his work. Therefore, it is not for nothing that the sphere of art and culture has risen to the level of state policy in our country today. Decrees and decisions issued by our government in recent years directly serve to further develop this industry.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev addressed the participants of the international conference on the topic "Urgent issues of studying and promoting Uzbek classic and modern literature at the international level" and said, "If literature, art and culture live, the nation and the people, the fact that the whole of humanity lives in peace" is an indication that it is an important social issue to pay attention to literature and art in the education of our young people in all aspects.

It should be noted that art should reflect beauty, goodness and goodness. Enthusiastic about art and culture, souls always strive for goodness. It is necessary for artists to be able to see the inner beauty in the human heart and share goodness with it. The purpose of art is to provide spiritual nourishment and lead a person to moral perfection.

Preservation of our national art and culture and passing it on to future generations is one of the urgent tasks of today. Its implementation is the sacred duty of every intellectual representative of our country.

Not only the educational institution, but also the family plays a big role in raising teenagers in the spirit of patriotism. The views of the child depend on the patriotic feelings and views of the parents. Accordingly, there is a problem of organizing patriotic education at all age stages of development: preschool education and upbringing, schoolchildren, students and representatives of the older generation.

To deeply study and discuss the treatises created by Eastern scientists and thinkers in various areas of art and culture, to justify the fact that the scientific heritage created by them is the basis for the development of almost all fields of science, science and culture throughout the world, and through it Cultivating the feelings of national pride, pride, and love for the Motherland in the minds of the younger generation is one of the main tasks of literature and music education.

Fiction is a unique means and source of mastering the world. In this respect, it approaches science. It is distinguished from it by its imagery in the reflection of the world. Fiction always shows the world in a way that is rich in instructions. The most important thing is that they have an aesthetic taste and peace, a spiritual lesson that affects the heart of the student. All this leads to the formation of high spiritual feelings in the student's heart and the spiritual satisfaction that is created by enjoying them.

Fiction is an important factor in enriching the human spiritual world. By teaching fiction at school, students' artistic taste, ability to think independently, love of reading, and sense of responsibility for the fate of the Motherland are nurtured and matured. By studying the works of writers and analyzing their works, the teacher arouses the interest of the students in knowing and identifying the moral-elegance issues raised in those works. In order for students to have a sense of interest, it is natural for them to acquire the art of expressive and literary reading of works of various genres, the ability to express the content of the works they read orally and in writing, and to acquire the skills of storytelling, literature they should understand that the art of speech is an artistic expression of life. For this, the teacher should master the methods of school literature teaching, be aware of scientific, literary-theoretical knowledge. The school does not limit itself to providing general education to students, it also develops independent thinking skills, which is a necessary condition for creative work, and develops and perfects a sense of high approach to every work. The main goal of educating students is to make them pious and religious by thoroughly instilling the basics of science into their minds, to educate them to have a conscious approach to every event in social life, and to develop the ability

to apply the acquired knowledge and skills to life. . In this regard, the literature lesson is a means of educating the young generation in the spirit of high ideals that our society is promoting.

Literature as an educational subject is complex and multifaceted. It adapts students to life, develops in them a sense of interest in seeing and understanding life, the ability to understand the complexity of the environment and human character, forms and develops a sense of loyalty to the homeland and people. The study of literature as an academic subject is carried out by analyzing the work and identifying the literary, moral, and philosophical issues that the writer put in it. The teacher helps the students to understand the interdependence of the parts of the work, to express their opinions coherently orally and in writing based on evidence.

Bright historical events and images of historical figures that shape the scientific worldview also enrich the spiritual world of students, increase the feeling of contributing to the development of the material wealth and spiritual culture of society. Accordingly, in addition to the history lesson, literature lessons are studied in connection with geography, visual arts, and music. In this way, students will develop the skills of independent understanding of events of social life, works of literature and art, and a coherent worldview. The concept of patriotism is broad and multifaceted, and the tasks set for patriotic education of students can be solved using various tools and by organizing appropriate pedagogical conditions. One of them is music.

"Music is a necessary spiritual attribute of human existence," said Aristotle. There are many opportunities for developing patriotic feelings in musical education of students. Musical tools help to reveal the abilities of each student, his creative potential, and ultimately foster a sense of pride in his country. The tool of patriotic education can be not only the words of songs, but also works of art, selected according to the age, which are combined with the sound of listening music. Music is able to retain visual impressions for a long time. It is impossible to develop love for the motherland without cultivating love and respect for the mother. Songs about mother are constantly included in the repertoire of students, they evoke sincere and direct feelings of students.

The richness and diversity of the content of the students' folklore contributes to the patriotic education of the students. Using Uzbek folk songs and melodies while listening to music, they attract students with their artistic and cognitive properties. Thus, the art of folk music is a powerful source of education and training, which is included in the daily life of students and has become an

integral part of the development of patriotism. A student who feels and understands music, likes to sing and dance, loves the world around him and nature, so he cannot be careless, rude and cruel.

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